

ABSTRACT BOOK

International research
and practice conference:

**NANOTECHNOLOGY
AND NANOMATERIALS
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Lviv, Ukraine

**INTERNATIONAL RESEARCH
AND PRACTICE CONFERENCE
“NANOTECHNOLOGY
AND NANOMATERIALS”**

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to the International Year of Basic Sciences
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Lviv, UKRAINE

Abstract book

Mechanical spectroscopy of nanocomposites of multiwalled carbon nanotubes and polyamide, polyethylene, polyvinyl chloride, porous polystyrene

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The influence of ultrasonic (US) deformation ε_{US} was studied on inelastic internal friction (IF) Q^{-1} and elastic modulus E of nanocomposite polyamide-6 (PA-6) $(NH(CH_2)_5CO)_n + 1.7\%$ methylene dye blue squaring (DBSQ) in Fig. 1 [1].

Fig. 1. Illustration of the window for processing data of quasi-transversal elastic wave velocity measuring $V_{\perp} = 1215$ m/sec in nanocomposite polyamide-6 (PA-6) $(NH(CH_2)_5CO)_n + 1.7\%$ methylene dye blue squaring

Conclusions

1. The increase of the nanocomposite crystallinity degree at growth of multiwalled carbon nanotubes concentration filling with the methylene dye blue squaring of matrix results in the decline of content of organized phase.

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1. Onanko A. P., Kuryliuk V. V., Onanko Y. A. et al. Peculiarity of elastic and inelastic properties of radiation cross-linked hydrogels // J. Nano- and Elec. Phys.-2020.-12, № 4.- P. 4026(1)-4026(5).

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